

Limits to Growth revisited: world economic development and distributional implications in the 21st century

Abstract

We use a system dynamics environment-economy model to explore how multiple limits to growth might affect global economic output and consumption across different social classes until 2100. Based on a five-dimensional scenario space, we simulate global economic development in 120 scenarios that differ in labor productivity growth, per-capita consumption growth, fossil resource availability, climate change severity, and climate system sensitivity. In 92% of the simulations, output peaks and then declines persistently. Excluding scenarios without climate impacts, output in 2100 is 15–70% lower than in 2019. Scenarios with low labor productivity and consumption growth experience earlier peaks at lower levels and moderate output declines. In contrast, scenarios with high labor productivity and consumption growth show faster and longer periods of growth but eventually face economic collapse. While resource depletion and climate damages act as stressors, most simulations indicate that growth ultimately halts and reverses due to a shortage of labor hours. During the phase of unintentional economic degrowth, economic convergence and redistribution reduce consumption in high-income countries to values 3–4 times lower than initial consumption levels, while middle- and low-income countries return to consumption levels similar to those at the start of the simulations. Poverty reduction in poorer regions ends as global output peaks, while environmental destabilization caused by economic growth threatens development opportunities beyond the 21st century.

Keywords

Limits to growth; system dynamics; labor productivity; post-growth; integrated assessment modeling; global environmental scenarios

1. Introduction

The publication of *The Limits to Growth* (LTG) report (Meadows et al., 1972), sparked heated debates within academia and broader society (Higgs, 2022), and pioneered the use of computer-based integrated modeling to explore future global environmental and socio-economic dynamics (Cassen & Cointe, 2022; Vieille Blanchard, 2010). With the rise of climate change the growth-versus-environment debated has experienced a revival although the debate has shifted from concerns about resource depletion to the transgression of planetary boundaries as well as to non-biophysical factors limiting economic growth in the Anthropocene, such as social or political factors (Butler, 2024; Döring & Aigner-Walder, 2022; Jackson & Webster, 2017; Scheffran, 2023; Van Den Bergh, 2017).

Since the original publication of the World3 model, simulations were updated twice by the MIT research team (Meadows et al., 1992, 2004) and were replicated and updated by other independent researchers (Herrington, 2021; Turner, 2008, 2014). An uncertainty analysis of World3 found high sensitivity of output variables but stable trends, indicating a low probability of favorable futures for humankind (Heath et al., 2019). Likewise, a recent recalibration of the model indicates a collapse dynamic due to resource depletion that occurs with a temporal delay and after a higher peak, compared to the original simulations (Nebel et al., 2024). An extension of World3 was developed to simulate the effects of a rapid scaling of Artificial Intelligence on the limits to growth (Guliyeva et al., 2025) while a regionalized simulation of World3's 'runaway global warming' scenario shows an unequal distribution of deaths by starvation over the world (Richards et al., 2023). World3 has also inspired the development of new models such as the Integrated Global Food and Energy Security System Dynamics Model by Pasqualino et al. (2019) that was created by merging structures of World3 with a macroeconomic and an energy model, the World3-based World Energy Model by Ansell & Cayzer (2018) built to examine changes in the energy and climate system, the Earth4All model that includes social variables like a social tension and a well-being index (Stoknes et al., 2025). Further models developed to study limits to growth include WoLim (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2015) and MEDEAS (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2020). Many studies also have applied fundamental concerns of the original LTG simulations to specific sectors, such as the agriculture (Khorsandi et al., 2023) or space sector (Miraux, 2022), and have studied different potential limiting factors that have become more relevant due to recent economic and political developments such as energy efficiency (Murphy, 2022), mineral resource availability (Valero et al., 2018) and the deployment of negative emission technologies (Gambhir et al., 2023). Despite these modeling efforts and a certain reappraisal of the LTG study, international policy-making arguably is still heavily influenced by the discourse of green growth, which dismisses the possibility of collapse, assuming the feasibility of strong decoupling and continued growth in consumption and production (Gómez-Baggethun & Naredo, 2015; Smith & Ely, 2025).

This paper aims to contribute to the literature and debate on LTG by illustrating the main dynamics of a series of simulations conducted with a newly developed system dynamics model called MORDRED (Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development). Specifically, we seek to assess whether global collapse remains a plausible outcome within the twenty-first century (1), and to analyze how potential collapse trajectories could differentially affect living standards across social groups and regions (2). Our modeling work makes three contributions to the state of the art: First, consumption in the model is disaggregated by class and by region to address concerns raised by Global South voices that stressed the importance of economic inequality in the context of debates on (limits to) world development, which are

rendered invisible in aggregated global models (Bull & Aguilar-Støen, 2023; Grondona, 2024; Jones, 2022). Second, the model focuses on concrete changes in biophysical and technological variables, and is capable of simultaneously representing the effects of the energy transition and of unfolding climate damages on emission and temperature pathways. Third, in contrast to existing LTG related studies that sidestep the economic input factor labor or assume labor is never scarce, we treat labor, mediated by changes in population and productivity, as a key potential limiting factor to growth.

2. Methods

2.1. The MORDRED model

For our simulations, we use version 1.1.2 of the MORDRED model (*Model of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development*). The model structure, mathematical equations, and data sources are described in detail by Lauer & Llases (2025). Therefore, for reasons of space, we provide only a description of the modules and variables most relevant to our scenario analysis.

MORDRED is a system dynamics model programmed in Vensim, designed to represent global-scale socio-economic dynamics and their interaction with the biophysical environment. The model consists of several modules describing the world population, economy, labor force, energy sources, land types (including natural ecosystems and economically used land), environmental stressors such as greenhouse gases, and the climate system.

The demographic module, built with UN population data (UN DESA, 2019b, 2019a, 2019c) and Exiobase3 data on household and government consumption (Stadler et al., 2018), computes the evolution of the global population, divided into three regions: the center (C) (all high-income countries), the semi-periphery (S) (all upper-middle-income countries), and the periphery (P) (all remaining countries). Population dynamics depend on age-specific birth and death rates, which are influenced by per capita consumption and public spending on education and health. These differ across world regions and among social classes within each region. At each simulation step, the population sustained by the global economy — whose labor serves as input to global production — is divided into the richest 20 % (R20), the poorest 30 % (P30), and the middle class (M50), comprising the remaining 50 %. This yields nine per-capita consumption trajectories globally.

The economic module follows an input–output structure where production is determined by final demand and factors such as technological change, climate impacts, and resource constraints. Final demand, computed globally and divided into 25 sectors, consists of private consumption, public consumption, and investment.

Private consumption is driven by the consumption demand of each social class, defined exogenously by specifying a desired growth rate for the P30 class and relative consumption multipliers linking other classes to it. The desired per capita consumption for each class and region ($Cp_{r,cl}$) evolves according to equation (1), where $Cp_{nc_{r,cl}}$ denotes the desired consumption not covered by production (see equation (20)). The distribution of per capita consumption across the 25 sectors (i) is calculated with a vector denoting the sectoral share of total per capita consumption ($Cpc_{ssh_{r,cl,i}}$), estimated based on Exiobase3 sectoral private consumption data for different world regions, reflecting different consumption levels (2).

Multiplying sectoral per capita consumption by population yields total consumption per class and region (3). Aggregating across classes and regions gives desired global private consumption by sector (4-5).

$$Cpc_{r,cl}^d = \int_{t_0}^t (Cpc_{r,cl}^d \cdot Cpc_{gr,cl} - Cpc_{nc,cl}) dt + Cpc_{r,cl}^d(t_0) \quad (1)$$

$$Cpc_{r,cl,i}^d = Cpc_{r,cl}^d \cdot Cpc_{ssh,r,cl,i} \quad (2)$$

$$C_{r,cl,i}^d = Cpc_{r,cl,i}^d \cdot P_r \cdot share_{cl} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{r,i}^d = \sum_{cl} C_{r,cl,i}^d \quad (4)$$

$$C_i^d = \sum_r C_{r,i}^d \quad (5)$$

Desired public consumption per region (G_r^d) is defined as a share ($G2Cr_r$) of total desired private consumption per region that reflects Exiobase3 data for 2019 aggregated at the regional level (6). A constant sectoral distribution is applied for each region (7), and desired global public consumption by sector is obtained by aggregating across regions (8).

$$G_r^d = C_r^d \cdot G2Cr_r \quad (6)$$

$$G_{r,i}^d = G_r^d \cdot G_{ssh,r,i} \quad (7)$$

$$G_i^d = \sum_r G_{r,i}^d \quad (8)$$

Investment is calculated by sector at the global level and aims to maintain a specific capital stock-output ratio for each sector. It depends on sectoral capital intensity, production, and the depreciation rate of capital. Both capital intensity and depreciation have endogenous and exogenous components: the exogenous component evolves according to scenario assumptions while the endogenous component is influenced by environmental changes such as climate change impacts caused by a rise in global average temperatures ($temp$) or sea level rise (slr), and fossil resource depletion ($depl$). Capital intensity is calculated using equation (9), where β_i is a sector-specific damage factor influenced by temperature-related output losses in the food sector, and depletion-related fossil resource extraction difficulties in the fossil resource sectors, and $Int_i^{k,wod}$ denotes the capital intensity without damage. Sectoral depreciation is given by equation (10). Sectoral investment is then calculated using sectoral output in the previous time step, sectoral capital stock, and an adjustment parameter that regulates the investment speed to ensure that the investment is not concentrated in a single period (11). The capital stock increases with investment and decreases with depreciation (12).

The sum of investment across all sectors yields total investment. Subsequently, to calculate gross fixed capital formation as a demand component, total investment is multiplied by a vector indicating which share of the total production of investment goods belongs to each sector. Additional GFCF becomes necessary when the global temperature increase exceeds 2°C compared to pre-industrial levels.

$$Int_i^k = Int_i^{k,wod} * \beta_i^{temp,depl} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_i = \delta_i^{wod} + \delta_i^{temp} + \delta_i^{slr} \quad (10)$$

$$Inv_i^d = \max(0; \beta^{Inv} \cdot (X_i^s(ts - 1) \cdot Int_i^k - K_i) + \delta_i \cdot K_i) \quad (11)$$

$$K_i = \int_{t_0}^t (Inv_i^s - \delta_i \cdot K_i) dt + K_i(t_0) \quad (12)$$

$$GFCF_i^d = GFCF_ssh_i \cdot \sum_i (Inv_i^d) + Extra_GFCF^{slr} \quad (13)$$

The sum of the three demand components yields final demand (14). Output required to meet this demand is computed using the global input-output table of the model that evolves according to exogenous parameters reflecting assumptions about technological change, and endogenous variables such as increasing fossil resource extraction difficulties and climate change impacts in the food sector. Output by sector is derived via the Leontief inverse (15).

$$FD_i^d = C_i^d + G_i^d + GFCF_i^d \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{X}^d = (Id - A)^{-1} \cdot \overline{FD}^d \quad (15)$$

From the desired output by sector, the required inputs of land, energy, and labor are determined in the respective modules. The maximum available labor depends on the working-age population (15–64 years), participation rates, and hours worked, while labor demand depends on sectoral productivity. Land availability depends on the share of inhabitable land already in use, while land demand depends on land intensities, both of which are affected by climate change.

Because the model uses a Leontief production function, shortages in any input factor lead to proportional reductions in output. A scarcity factor (Sf), ranging from 0 to 1, is computed in each of the corresponding modules; the smallest of these is then multiplied by the demanded output to determine the actual - supplied (s) - output (16), (17). The smallest scarcity factor is also applied to final demand to calculate the actual satisfied final demand (18), as well as to the productive factors to determine the resources that have actually been used.

$$Sf = \min(Sf^{Lb}; Sf^{ff}; Sf^{Lnd}) \quad (16)$$

$$X_i^s = X_i^d \cdot Sf \quad (17)$$

$$FD_i^s = FD_i^d \cdot Sf \quad (18)$$

When total desired demand exceeds what available resources can produce, consumption across all classes is reduced proportionally to maintain consumption ratios between classes determined by convergence assumptions. Per capita consumption for each class and region is derived by dividing the consumption allocated to the corresponding group by its population, which constitutes a certain share of the total population ($clsh$) (19). The per capita consumption not covered ($Cpc_nr_{r,cl}$) is computed as the difference between the demanded and supplied per capita consumption (20).

$$Cpc_{r,cl}^s = \frac{\sum_i (C_{r,cl,i}^s)}{P_r * clsh_{cl}} \quad (19)$$

$$Cpc_nr_{r,cl} = Cpc_{r,cl}^d - Cpc_{r,cl}^s \quad (20)$$

The energy and stressor modules calculate the total amount of fossil resources extracted to produce total output, an extraction difficulty factor reflecting increasing resource depletion, and the corresponding greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, mainly based on IEA data (IEA, 2021). The

stressor module also calculates emissions of other GHGs (CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, HFC, PFC) based on sectoral emission intensity data from the environmental extensions of Exiobase3.

The different GHG emissions are fed into the climate module, which is adapted from the Integrated Assessment Model WILIAM (Lifi et al., 2023) and has been actualized with the latest IPCC (2021) data. In this module, the increase in the global average temperature is calculated and fed back into the economy, labor and land modules.

2.2. Scenario design

For our scenario analysis, we consider five key variables that may influence the timing, pace, and scale of a decline in global economic output in response to different limits to growth: the growth in sectoral labor productivities, growth in consumption per capita across social classes, accessibility of fossil resources, the presence of climate damages, and the sensitivity of the climate system to anthropogenic perturbations. By defining a plausible range of values for each variable, a five-dimensional scenario space is constructed that covers all possible scenarios resulting from variations in the main variables' values (Fig. 1). Each main variable can take a medium state, reflecting our best guess (BG) about the model parameters, as well as a 'low' or 'high' state, corresponding to the lower and upper bounds of a plausible range. Combining different variables in various states produces unique scenarios that can be compared in terms of the model's main outputs. For example, comparing a scenario characterized by low labor productivity growth, medium consumption growth, low fossil resource accessibility, low climate damages, and medium climate sensitivity with another differing only in higher fossil resource accessibility allows us to explore how resource availability drives potential growth and unintentional degrowth patterns in global output.

In MORDRED 1.1.2, labor productivities in the 25 economic sectors are calculated by inverting sectoral labor intensities (21). Changes in labor intensities are represented by an exponentially decaying function of average per capita consumption at the global level for each sector, with the latter serving as an indicator of economic development associated with lower average labor intensities (22).

$$Lprod_i = \frac{1}{Lint_i} \quad (21)$$

$$Lint_i = \alpha_i * e^{\beta_i * CpC_{world\ average}} \quad (22)$$

To derive the lower bound for labor productivity growth, the parameters of these functions are fitted to regional and global labor productivities and consumption levels in 2019, using EXIOBASE3 data aggregated into a high-income region and a world region. The parameters ensure that global sectoral labor productivities increase with rising average global consumption, reaching high-income country levels once global average consumption attains 97% of that of high-income countries. To calculate the BG for conceivable growth in sectoral labor productivities, the α parameter for each sector is reduced by 10%, resulting in higher productivities for a given consumption level. For the upper bound, α_i is reduced by 20%. The resulting scenario space reflects optimistic assumptions regarding future labor productivity growth since α_i is always lowered rather than increased.

As BG for consumption growth, we assume that by 2100 the per capita consumption levels in the periphery equal those of the center in 2019, that the semiperiphery is 25% above 2019 center

levels, and that consumption in the center increases by 50%. For the lower bound, consumption in the center remains constant while the semiperiphery and periphery reach 75% and 50% of the center's consumption, respectively. For the upper bound, desired consumption in the center increases by 100%, while the semiperiphery and periphery reach 150% and 125% of 2019 center levels.

We use fossil reserves and resource estimates from BGR (2020) as the quantitative basis for fossil resource availability. Limited substitutability between fuel types and low coal accessibility define the lower bound, while perfect substitutability and high coal accessibility define the upper bound. The BG assumes perfect substitutability and medium coal accessibility. Consequently, in low-accessibility scenarios, input factors in fossil extraction sectors increase by 30% when all reserves are depleted. In BG and high-accessibility cases, input costs remain stable until all reserves are depleted but rise by 75% when all oil and gas resources and 10% of coal are extracted (BG) and by 50% when all oil and gas and 60% of coal are extracted (high). Our lower bound for fossil resources is 1.6 times higher than that in Turner's (2008) while our upper bound is 2.48 to 4.95 times higher, reflecting a certain optimism about future fossil resource availability.

For climate damages, the BG corresponds to the model's default values for all damage parameters. In the low-damages case, parameters regulating damages to capital stock and output are reduced by 25%, the parameter value causing increases in input coefficients is reduced by 8%, parameters influencing labor productivity and labor supply are reduced by 30%, and climate-induced losses of land and land productivity by 25%. In the high-damage case, the parameters impacting capital stock and output increase by 25%, the parameter impacting input coefficients increases by 10%, and the parameters influencing labor and land increase by 20% and 25%, respectively. To test extreme conditions, we also allow simulations without climate damages, though such cases are not considered plausible.

The climate sensitivity variable determines how strongly and rapidly the climate system reacts to anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Higher sensitivity results in greater temperature increases under a given anthropogenic emission pathway. When sensitivity is low, feedback mechanisms are deactivated, and the equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) is set to 3 °C. For medium sensitivity, the ECS remains unchanged, but feedback mechanisms are activated, enhancing natural carbon and methane emissions. High climate sensitivity is obtained by activating feedbacks and increasing ECS by 10%, reflecting an increased climate sensitivity found in more recent climate modeling studies (Wyser et al., 2020).

Supplementary Material (SM) 1 contains additional boundary conditions common to all scenarios.

Fig. 1: Simplified representation of the scenario space constructed with the five main variables. Each variable is represented by colored bidirectional arrows indicating its value range. The left/low ends indicate 'low' states, while the right/high ends indicate 'high' states.

To simulate scenarios across the full scenario space, we divide it along labor productivity and consumption growth and simulate four scenario sets (Table 1). The first two include all scenarios with low or high labor productivity growth and medium (BG) consumption growth; the last two include scenarios with low or high consumption growth and medium (BG) labor productivity growth. We also simulate scenarios without climate damages for these four sets. As climate sensitivity does not affect dynamics in the absence of climate damages, it is not varied. Each scenario set contains 30 scenarios, resulting in 120 simulations. The simulation period is identical for all scenarios and covers 2019–2100.

Consumption growth	low			medium (best guess)			high		
Labor productivity									
low				12101	12201	12301			
				12111	12211	12311			
				12112	12212	12312			
				12113	12213	12313			
				12121	12221	12321			
				12122	12222	12322			
				12123	12223	12323			
				12131	12231	12331			
				12132	12232	12332			
				12133	12233	12333			
medium (best guess)	21101	21201	21301				23101	23201	23301
	21111	21211	21311				23111	23211	23311
	21112	21212	21312				23112	23212	23312

	21113	21213	21313		23113	23213	23313
	21121	21221	21321		23121	23221	23321
	21122	21222	21322		23122	23222	23322
	21123	21223	21323		23123	23223	23323
	21131	21231	21331		23131	23231	23331
	21132	21232	21332		23132	23232	23332
	21133	21233	21333		23133	23233	23333
high			32101	32201	32301		
			32111	32211	32311		
			32112	32212	32312		
			32113	32213	32313		
			32121	32221	32321		
			32122	32222	32322		
			32123	32223	32323		
			32131	32231	32331		
			32132	32232	32332		
			32133	32233	32333		

Table 1: Each five-digit number represents a scenario. The first digit denotes labor productivity growth, the second denotes consumption growth, the third fossil resource availability, the fourth climate damages, and the fifth climate sensitivity. (1) indicates a low value, (2) a medium/BG value, and (3) a high value. (0) is used only for climate damages to denote the absence of damages.

3. Results

We present the development of total economic output before proceeding to the differentiated impacts of emerging limits to growth on different social classes and world regions. Due to the input–output framework of the economic model, output is the sum of industry demand for intermediate products and final demand.

3.1. Projected development of world economic production

The most general indicator in MORDRED showing changes in world economic production is the total annual output at the global level, calculated by the economic module. The simulations show that an end of economic growth, followed by a period of persistent decline in world economic production, is a characteristic of 92% of all scenarios. Excluding the scenarios without climate damages, this figure rises to 99%, with the only exception being scenario *32311*, characterized by low climate sensitivity and damages, high fossil resource availability, medium consumption growth, and high labor productivity growth. This scenario is linked to the highest output among all simulated cases, although consumption is lower than in the scenarios without climate damage impacts, indicating that a greater share of economic activity must be dedicated to countering the effects of increasing climate damage and resource scarcity. However, compared to other scenarios, the pressure on the economy is still low enough to be buffered by high labor productivity levels—at least during the simulation period, when such pressures can still be offset by productivity gains.¹ Apart from the lack of climate damages, the great majority of scenarios that grow continuously until 2100 are characterized by medium or high fossil resource availability, with the only exception being scenario *21101*.

¹ Extending the simulation period between 2100, we find that this scenario collapses abruptly in 2103.

Thus, unless it is assumed that climate change impacts do not exist, or that industrial processes radically ‘dematerialize’ in unspecified ways—rendering economic production structures incomparable with current processes—an end to economic growth followed by a period of persistent economic decline can be expected to occur during the 21st century. Importantly, these findings apply only to the global level, as MORDRED does not disaggregate production into different world regions. Hence, earlier peaks and declines in some regions, as well as continued growth in others, may still be compatible with the simulation results.

Regarding changes in output compared to the start of the simulation, in 89% of the simulated scenarios output levels at the end of the period are lower than at the start, while output exceeds initial levels in only 13 scenarios, three of which peak and decline in the 2080s. All 13 scenarios are characterized by low climate sensitivity, and all but one by the absence of climate change impacts. Of all scenarios with a peak and subsequent decline, output is highest in scenarios *12101* and *32101*: by 2100, global output remains 1.86 times higher than in 2019. The scenario with the lowest output in 2100 is *32211*, where output is 70% lower than initially.

Fig. 2a-d shows the evolution of output for each scenario set. The scenario sets exhibit clear differences in both the timing and level of the peak in global output.

In the set with low labor productivity (and medium consumption) growth (Fig. 2a) output peaks earliest, with most scenarios peaking between 2035 and 2050. This is followed by the set with (medium labor productivity and) high consumption growth (Fig. 2d) where the first peak occurs in 2040. The first scenario in the set featuring (medium labor productivity and) low consumption growth peaks in 2043 (Fig. 2c) while the earliest peak in the set with high labor productivity (and medium consumption growth) occurs in 2049 (Fig. 2b). Under equal consumption growth rates, lower labor productivity growth leads to earlier peaks, as the point of labor scarcity caused by emerging limiting factors is reached sooner. Conversely, under equal labor productivity growth, higher consumption growth results in faster increases in emissions and temperatures, faster growth in damages, and earlier labor shortages.

While all scenarios with low labor productivity growth and some level of climate damage reach their maximum output within 15 years after the first scenario peaks, scenarios with high labor productivity growth show peaks over a 50-year span, including two late peaks in the 2080s and 2090s, followed by steep collapses in the cases of medium and low fossil resource accessibility (*32211* and *32111*). Both scenario sets built on low and high consumption growth see peaks and declines within approximately four decades. The output level at the peak is lowest in the low-consumption set and highest in the high-labor productivity set. Scenarios with low labor productivity and medium consumption growth tend to peak at lower levels than scenarios with medium labor productivity and high consumption growth, although those combining no climate damages with low fossil resources peak at comparable levels.

Thus, higher labor productivity growth rates increase the level at which output peaks because they allow output to grow longer, while higher consumption growth rates lead to higher peaks because output rises faster. At the same time, low labor productivity and consumption growth rates are associated with slower output reductions, creating ‘smooth’ curves, while high growth—especially high labor productivity growth—produces faster and steeper declines resembling collapse dynamics. This dynamic arises from the endogenization of labor productivity: as output grows, rising productivity allows further expansion despite emerging limits such as climate damages and resource constraints. Paradoxically, limiting factors can initially increase output growth, as they lower the ratio between final demand and output,

requiring higher output to meet desired consumption. However, once labor shortages emerge, output declines, reducing productivity further and creating a self-reinforcing downward spiral. The longer non-labor limiting factors accumulate before output peaks, the greater the subsequent economic decline.

Excluding scenarios without climate change, the 2100 output range is lowest for scenarios with high labor productivity (47.4–100.8 trillion €) and highest for scenarios with low consumption (70.1–132 trillion €). The sets with high consumption (66.7–104.7 trillion €) and low labor productivity (69.2–117.6 trillion €) fall in between. However, even in the sets with the highest final output range, the values remain significantly below the initial output of 156 trillion €.

Fig. 2: Evolution of world output throughout all simulations. Scenario sets with a) low labor productivity, b) high labor productivity, c) low consumption, d) high consumption growth.

Having highlighted differences in world economic trajectories caused by varying labor productivity and consumption growth rates, we now turn to the role of resource availability, climate damages and climate sensitivity. Fig. 3a-d shows the four scenario sets with the color indicating the fossil resource availability in the scenarios. Differences in the economic trajectories between scenarios with medium or high fossil resource availability are relatively low across all scenario sets. Scenarios with low resource availability, however, tend to peak earlier. This is especially evident in the case of scenarios with no climate damages where rising extraction difficulties cause output to decline in all scenario sets except for the one with low consumption growth rates (Fig. 3c). Thus, even when climate impacts on the economy are judged insignificant, for example due to extremely high assumed adaptation capacities of society, resource constraints can still bring economic growth to a halt. In general, in scenarios with low resource accessibility the input costs of the extraction sectors increase earlier, resulting directly and indirectly (through an increase in labor intensity of the extraction sectors as well as through the necessary growth in intermediate goods and investment) in a higher labor demand, which, in combination with climate impacts, is sufficient to cause a scarcity of labor hours. Additionally, once output levels approach 500 trillion 2019-€ per year, the fossil resources have been depleted to such an extent that an additional fossil scarcity factor begins to apply in the model that slows down growth to avoid a sudden crash as accessible resources approach zero. Due to its lower consumption growth, scenario 21101 is not affected by this dynamic, reaching similar

levels of output as the scenario variants with higher resource availability. Scenarios 12201, 12301, 32201 and 32301 reach the same output in 2100 independently from energy resource availability and labor productivity growth rates since all scenarios have the same desired consumption growth rates that can be fulfilled due to the absence of climate damages and higher resource availability than in scenario 12101.

The effects of climate damages and climate sensitivity are clearly visible in Fig. 3e-h and Fig. 3i-l. They both work in the same direction, and their combined effect is the main driver shaping global economic trajectories in the simulations. Across all simulations and scenario sets, scenarios with high climate damages *ceteris paribus* have the earliest peaks in world output, followed by scenarios with medium, low and no damages. The same applies to climate sensitivity: the higher the sensitivity, the earlier the peak in output occurs.

These findings reflect basic reasoning: The higher the level of damage given a certain temperature increase, the earlier climate change will start to adversely impact economic trajectories. Likewise, the higher the sensitivity of the climate system to anthropogenic perturbations, the higher the global warming response to a given emission pathway, leading to higher climate damages at every given level of emissions. Given that emission pathways are, *inter alium*, driven by output, a higher sensitivity leads to climate damages starting to impact the economy at comparatively lower levels of world output.

Unsurprisingly, scenarios with high damages and high sensitivity peak first in all scenario sets, independent from fossil resource accessibility. The reason is that the combined effect of high damages and high sensitivity lead output to peak before extraction costs start to rise in the case of low resource accessibility. Even when extraction costs begin to rise the effect on the output trajectory is negligible due to the small share of the extraction sectors in total output.

Thus, lower labor productivity growth combined with lower resource accessibility, higher consumption growth, higher damages and higher climate sensitivities accelerates a peak and decline of world economic production while higher labor productivity levels and resource accessibility combined with lower consumption, damages and sensitivity can delay this dynamic, although they might also cause a steeper and more abrupt decline resembling economic collapse.

Fig. 3: Evolution of output in trillion € throughout all scenario simulations (grey dots). a)-d): Scenarios with low (pink dots), medium (yellow dots) and high (dark green dots) fossil resource accessibility. e)-h): Scenarios with high (pink dots), medium (yellow dots), low (dark green dots) and no (light green dots) climate impacts (pink dots). i)-l): Scenarios with high (pink dots), medium (yellow dots) and low (dark green dots) climate sensitivity. a), e), i): Colored dots represent scenarios with low labor productivity growth. b), f), j): Colored dots represent scenarios with high labor productivity growth. c), g), k): Colored dots represent scenarios with low consumption growth. d), h), l): Colored dots represent scenarios with high consumption growth.

3.2. Differentiated impacts of decline in world economic output

Given that in the current economic system the distribution of economic goods between social classes is highly unequal, different socio-economic groups might see themselves affected by a decline in world output in different ways. In our simulations, in the absence of limits to growth, a certain convergence in consumption between social classes takes place as the consumption of poorer classes grows at a higher rate than the consumption of richer classes (see SM1). In the case of emerging limits to growth, this convergence process is maintained, reflecting the optimistic assumption that in times of economic recessions and production decline redistribution aims at buffering the impacts for the poorer classes.

Fig. 4 shows the consumption per capita trajectories for three different social classes in 12 scenarios covering all scenario sets as well as low, medium and high climate impacts. Simulation results for the remaining scenarios are contained in SM2. Since consumption per capita pathways depend on the size of world output, consumption levels across all classes peak latest in scenarios with low climate impacts and reach the highest levels in scenarios with high labor productivity or high consumption growth. Unsurprisingly, the consumption pathways reproduce the same dynamics as the output trajectories, with high labor productivity and high consumption growth leading to higher consumption levels and steeper declines of per capita

consumption. Irrespective of the scenario set, at the global level, the decline in consumption following the peak is highest in the richest class and lowest in the poorest (Fig. 4a, e, i). However, while the richest 20% of the center remain above a consumption threshold of 10 € per day (Fig. 4a-d), the poorest 30% of the periphery never cross this consumption threshold, except for a period of less than 20 years in a scenario with high labor productivity growth and low climate impacts. The consumption of the middle class in the semiperiphery starts crosses the 10€-threshold during the phase of economic growth in every scenario set. However, during the period of global unintentional degrowth in output, consumption declines again and by the end of the simulation is below the threshold, except for the scenario with low climate impacts and low consumption growth (Fig. 4g). At the same time, public expenditures that might complement private consumption, such as health or education expenses per capita, are reduced as well, since they are modeled as a fixed share of household consumption at the regional level. Hence, scenarios with ongoing economic convergence throughout the whole simulation period avoid pushing the entire periphery into extreme poverty levels but at the same time strongly reduce consumption levels in the center. For example, in the 12 scenarios represented in Fig. 4, consumption levels of the richest 20% of the center in 2100 are between 72% and 85% lower than at the initial level, and between 72% and 86% lower compared to the moment where consumption levels reach their maximum. Conversely, consumption levels of the middle class of the semiperiphery at the end of the simulation are between 42% and 74% below the maximum levels reached during the simulation. Finally, the cut in consumption compared to the maximum level ranges between 24% and 71% for the poorest class of the periphery, with none of the consumption levels in 2100 being higher than 1500 € per year.

Fig. 4: Annual per capita consumption for the richest 20% of the center (a-d), the middle 50% of the semiperiphery (e-h) and the poorest 30% of the periphery (i-l) in 12 different scenarios: scenarios 12212, 12222 and 12232 in a), e) and i);

scenarios 32212, 32222 and 32232 in b), f) and j); scenarios 21212, 21222 and 21232 in c), g) and k); scenarios 23212, 23222 and 23232 in d), h) and l). Consumption pathways belonging to scenarios with low, medium and high climate impacts are colored in dark green, yellow and pink, respectively. The purple line denotes the consumption level corresponding to a per capita consumption of 10 € per day.

Fig. 5 complements Fig. 4 by displaying the consumption pathways of all social classes in MORDRED for the 'best guess' scenarios from every scenario set (12222, 32222, 21222, 23222), i.e. scenarios with medium resource accessibility, climate impacts and climate sensitivity. In all three regions, the richest 20% experience the highest declines in consumption in absolute terms but by the end of the century still have higher consumption levels than the poorer classes. Additionally, the three richest classes are the only classes that still consume more than 10 € per day in 2100. Comparing the consumption trajectories of the middle class in the center, semiperiphery and periphery illustrates that the consumption decline in relative terms is highest in the center since the middle class of the center has a much higher initial consumption level. However, while in the center the 10€-per-day consumption threshold is only approached by 2100 (Fig. 4b), in the semiperiphery it is already crossed between 2075 and 2085 (Fig. 4e). Finally, in the periphery, in the scenarios with low labor productivity and low consumption growth the decline in world economic output prevents the middle class from crossing the threshold in the first place (Fig. 4e). From 2075 onwards, consumption stabilizes in all scenarios between the 10€-per-day (purple line) and the 5€-per-day (orange line) threshold. The poorest classes in the three regions mirror the dynamics of the middle class but at a lower level of consumption. Around 2080, the consumption of the poorest 30% drops below the 10€-per-day threshold and by 2100, this class consumes less than the middle class of the semiperiphery in 2019 (Fig. 4c). In the semiperiphery, the consumption of the poorest class peaks at the 10€-threshold around 2060 in the high labor productivity growth scenario while the threshold is never crossed in the scenarios belonging to the other scenario sets. Between 2070 and 2100, the consumption has returned to the initial consumption values just below the 5€-threshold (Fig. 4f). Last, for the poorest class, consumption peaks at the 5€-threshold in the case of the low productivity and low consumption growth scenarios, and between the 5€- and the 10€-threshold in the case of the scenarios with high consumption and labor productivity growth. Thus, in the scenario simulations presented here, all classes of the center as well as the richest class of the semiperiphery see their consumption decline significantly below the initial level. As a result from ongoing global convergence, the consumption of the middle and poor class of the semiperiphery returns to the initial level while the consumption of all classes of the periphery stabilizes slightly above the initial level. Thus, the improvements in living standards and the reduction in the population living in poverty brought about by economic growth are short-lived. During the final three decades of the simulations, the low- and middle-income classes outside high-income countries become increasingly trapped in moderate to severe poverty. At the same time, the strong reductions in the living standards in the center constitute a radical break with historical tendencies. While situations of persistent poverty can remain compatible with societal and political stability as long as there are prospects for near-term economic growth, declines in living standards following a period of growth may undermine both social stability and the legitimacy of political systems. The results therefore point to two major potential sources of distributive conflict during the 21st century: the spread of poverty and the loss of prosperity attained during the period of economic growth. Neither higher economic growth nor moderate intra- and international redistribution can eliminate these sources of conflicts although the latter at least prevents a complete economic and demographic breakdown in the simulated scenarios.

Fig. 5: Per capita consumption pathways for a) the richest 20%, b) the middle 50%, c) the poorest 30% of the center; d) the richest 20%, e) the middle 50%, f) the poorest 30% of the semiperiphery; g) the richest 20%, h) the middle 50%, i) the poorest 30% of the periphery for four scenarios belonging to the scenario sets characterized by low labor productivity (dark red), high labor productivity (light red), low consumption (dark blue) and high consumption (light blue) growth. All scenarios are characterized by medium resource accessibility, climate impacts and climate sensitivity. The purple line denotes the consumption level corresponding to a per capita consumption of 10 € per day, the orange line represents a per capita consumption of 5 € per day.

4. Discussion

Our simulations indicate that plausible assumptions regarding the evolution of key socio-economic and environmental variables result in a high likelihood of a global economic peak followed by decline during the 21st century. Nevertheless, great uncertainty remains about the future evolution of important variables such as the accessibility of resources (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2016; Höök & Tang, 2013), unexpected developments in socio-technological systems (Krupa & Jones, 2013; Lenton et al., 2022) or the scale of climate impacts (Dankers & Kundzewicz, 2020; Frisch, 2018). Additionally, the model's empirical basis and structure render it incapable of

representing societal reactions and adaptation measures in response to emerging limits to growth (cf. Abbot & Malani, 2025; Cassen & Cointe, 2022). Thus, our results should not be interpreted as predictions regarding the timing of a global economic collapse but as a risk assessment illustrating that current socio-economic developments and the environmental changes they cause entail a significant risk of historical discontinuities and persistent declines in living standards. The deep uncertainty regarding the nature, scale and velocity of global environmental change, coupled with the impossibility of excluding socio-technological developments that seem implausible in today's system, makes it impossible to state that a decline in global output is unavoidable or that it would necessarily prove harmful or catastrophic. There always exists a possibility to change model parameters in a way as to avoid a 'collapse' during the 21st century, as shown, for example, in our simulations where climate impacts are negligible. Nevertheless, using a system dynamics model representing key feedback mechanisms between the global socio-economic and environmental system, we show that an end to global economic growth and a persistent decline during the 21st century is a possibility that should not be underestimated. Assuming this possibility means acknowledging that 'business as usual' will cease to work within the next 20 to 50 years, and that even a complete 'greening' of the electricity sector is insufficient to avoid limits to growth, given that all simulated scenarios include a shift to 100% renewable electricity by 2100.

From the perspective of economic, social and environmental policy design, our results raise several questions for scholars and policymakers in the coming decades: How can investment in key sectors and critical infrastructure be maintained during a prolonged global recession? Which international social policies can alleviate the spread of poverty implied by a persistent output decline? How can low-carbon provisioning systems deliver essential services without depending on growth? Which adaptation measures can mitigate heat- and weather-related impacts on labor productivity? Which policies foster the resilience and flexibility of production structures? Our results therefore highlight the importance of building bridges between the academic fields of post-growth (Burke, 2022; Kallis et al., 2025), resilience (Cumming & Peterson, 2017; Stanley, 2020) and climate vulnerability, impacts and adaptation (IPCC, 2022) to address these questions in an integrated way.

Not confounding our scenario analysis with probability-based predictions is crucial, as our simulations omit feedback mechanisms that could further constrain growth, and thus tend to underestimate historical discontinuities. Missing biophysical dynamics include the adverse impacts of crossing non-climate Earth system boundaries (Rockström et al., 2023), the limited availability of mineral resources (Sverdrup & Ragnarsdóttir, 2014) and limits to land productivity gains caused by soil depletion (DeLong et al., 2015; Shrivastava & Kumar, 2015; Wang et al., 2024), desertification (Ahmed et al., 2024; Cherlet et al., 2018) or scarcity of chemical fertilizers (Penuelas et al., 2023). Section 2 SM1 shows the ratio between land demanded by the economy and disposable land—i.e., the Earth's habitable land without water bodies—for 12 scenarios. Under constant land intensities, land demand surpasses disposable land in all scenarios, with maximum demand between 1.1 and 4 times total disposable land. Thus, unless rapid and persistent land productivity gains are assumed for the forestry, biomass and food sectors, limited habitable land could prove a key constraint to growth, influencing the entire economy through inter-industry linkages. Integrating biosphere and land-related limits becomes even more important in scenarios with stronger bioenergy-based decarbonization (Braun et al., 2025). On the social side, the model cannot represent geopolitical conflicts, migration, eroding institutional stability, civil wars or the global financial system—all elements of a polycrisis that could accelerate declines in output (Scheffran, 2025).

Despite these limitations, our simulations enrich the literature on quantitative modeling of socio-economic and environmental dynamics. By modeling labor availability as an endogenous variable dependent on demographic, economic and biophysical developments, we show the importance of labor as a potential limiting factor of economic growth. In our scenarios, it is not the absolute scarcity of resources or abstract environmental pollution that impairs production, but the simultaneous increase in labor demand and decline in labor supply driven by environmental degradation and resource depletion. Our model thus reflects that labor productivity growth depends on exergy (Furse, 2025) and that insufficient exergy can trigger collapse dynamics driven by falling labor productivity and falling resource extraction. At the same time, such dynamics could induce societal and economic restructuring processes altering simulated trajectories. Although our model grants labor a more central role in the LTG debate, uncertainty about sectoral labor productivity developments warrants further research—e.g., via simulations with differing assumptions about productivity drivers. Another contribution lies in modeling the differentiated impacts of global output decline on sub-global consumption levels. Our simulations show increased poverty risks for poorer classes and regions—the majority of the world’s population—even under optimistic assumptions of economic convergence during decline. Future work could explore whether early radical convergence reduces the spread of poverty, and whether divergence under unintended degrowth amplifies risks for systemic collapse, economic instability and extreme poverty driven by polarization triggered by emerging limits to growth.

Conclusion

In this study, we simulated 120 scenarios depicting non-linear developments in the global socio-economic and biophysical system throughout the 21st century. The results suggest that, under plausible assumptions about key variables, global economic output is likely to peak and subsequently decline within this century. Continued growth beyond 2100 occurs only under the highly improbable condition of no climate impacts combined with medium or high fossil resource availability.

These findings indicate that a ‘business-as-usual’ pathway is not viable: long-term global poverty eradication through economic growth alone cannot be achieved. As limits to growth emerge, the world will likely face declining consumption, rising poverty, depleted fossil resources, and a destabilized climate system constraining human development for millennia (Levermann et al., 2013; Xu et al., 2020). While the model cannot capture societal responses to these emerging limits, our simulations point to a high risk of distributive conflict within and between societies as consumption levels fall across all social classes. How such conflicts might unfold or be resolved lies beyond the scope of this scenario analysis.

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